

REPELLENT AND FEEDING DETERRENT ACTIVITY OF *CESTRUM* SPECIES AGAINST *TRIBOLIUM CASTANEUM* (HERBST)

Chetan Jawale* and M. U. Patil

Department of Zoology

Dr. B. A. Marathwada University

Aurangabad- 400001 (INDIA)

***Address for correspondence: - Chetan S Jawale “Radha Kunj” Visangi Nager,**

near Home Guard Office, JALGAON 425001 (M.S)

INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Methanol extract of *Cestrum* species viz., *Cestrum nocturnum* and *Cestrum diurnum* showed repellent activity and feeding deterrent activity to *Tribolium castaneum* at 1% conc. at three different doses. The extract showed complete feeding deterrent activity at 5 ml dose while complete repellent activity was noticed at 4 ml dose when the beetles were fed on wheat flour in the laboratory providing optimum temperature and humidity conditions. The detail experiment to isolate the bioactive compound is still progressive.

Key words: *Tribolium castaneum*, Repellent, Phagodeterrent, Bioactive principal, Methanol extracts, *Cestrum nocturnum*, *Cestrum diurnum*,

Introduction

During the last two decades large numbers of higher plants contain biological active principals with multifacial effects against various insects have been effectively demonstrated

by several researchers (Aarsion et al 1971; Pawar and Singh 1993; Sing 1993; Schmitt 1996). Extracts of plants have been used as insecticides by humans and a practice continue till today. Near about 2000 species of plants known to have insecticidal properties (Crosby 1975). In view of the presences of physiologically active alkaloids in the stem and leaves of *Cestrum parqui*^{22, 23}, the investigations was extended to the leaves of *Cestrum* species in India, The leaves of *Cestrum nocturnum* (Linn) (family- Solanaceae) commonly known as 'Night jasmine', have been found to be rich in saponin on purification they are establish to be yaccogenin²⁶ (207-8⁰c mp) and Tigogenin²⁴ (242-3⁰c mp) along with uroclilic acid²⁵ in leaves. The plant *Cestrum diurnum* (Linn) (Family- Solanaceae) a plant similar to *C. nocturnum*, grows wild in abundance throughout the country. Pharmacological examination of the saponin from the leaves of *C. nocturnum* showed that they control cardiac activity²⁸ similar to that of ouambin.

Since purified saponin are reported to passes various biological and pharmacological activity⁴ like antibacterial, fungicidal, antiviral, piscicidal, molluscicidal, cytotoxic, antitumor, antiinflammatory, insecticidal, antifertility antitussive analgesic etc. in present study plant *Cestrum nocturnum* ant *C. diurnum* were selected as repellent and feeding detorient plants against *Tribolium castenium*.

Material and Methods

For experimental bioassay the laboratory culture insect were used for repellent as well as antifeedant activity. For repellent activity visual observations were made on the adult insects on a spray treated filter paper (Whatsman). A number of insect used in the trial ranged ten in three replicate of each set. These insects were introduced into a petridish containing filter paper demarcated into A and B regions. Section A served as control which was treated

with ½ ml of methanol while section B with 2, 3, 4 ml doses of 1 % conc. Methanol extract of *C. nocturnum* and *C. diurnum*.

For antifeedant activity the wheat flour in 1 g was soaked for 24 hr in the above of three doses of 1% conc. of the extract. Five pairs adult *Tribolium castaneum* were released next day morning in each petridish in three replicates. Control was maintained with similar amount of wheat flour with ½ ml methanol.

OBSERVATION

Observations were recorded after every 24 hr interval for the repellent activity. In the completion of the experiment the loss in the weight of the flour was noted.

Table 1: Extent of feeding by *Tribolium castanum*

S. No.	Treatment	Percent of food loss		
		2 ml Dos	3 ml Dose	4 ml Dose
1.	Untreated	30	32	36
2.	Control with Methanol	15	18	20
3.	Treated with <i>C. nocturnum</i> extract	3.6	1.8	0
4.	Treated with <i>C. diurnum</i> extract	3.4	2.2	0

Table 2: Response of *Tribolium castaneum* to the extract of *Cestrum* species

S. No.	Treatment	Percentage of aggregation					
		2 ml Dose		3 ml Dose		4 ml Dose	
		Section A (Control)	Section B (Treated)	Section A (Control)	Section B (Treated)	Section A (Control)	Section B (Treated)

1	Untreated Control	48	62	58	42	56	44
2	with distilled methanol	60	40	40	60	69	51
3	Treated with <i>C. nocturnum</i> extract	82	18	96	4	100	0
4	Treated with <i>C. diurnum</i> extract	76	24	90	10	100	0

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From table 1, It appear that 4 ml dose of 1% conc. of both plant extract caused total inhibition of feeding to the *T. castaneum* whereas in the lower dose there was increases loss in the flour from 1.8 to 3 % in *C. nocturnum* while 2.2 to 3.4 % in *C. diurnum* which was lesser than the loss in weight in the methanol treated control flour. The result therefore indicates the more potent repellent activity as well as complete phagodetorient activity in *C. nocturnum* as compare to the *C. diurnum*. Whereas control 5 ml dose of 1% conc. is effective dose concentration for phagodetorient activity while 4 ml dose of 1% conc. is effective for the repellent of *T. castaneum*. Saraswathi and Rao,(!987) also reported the repellent effect of *Citronella* oil against *T. castaneum*, *Bruchus* and *Periplanata*, where the repellent activity persisted more than 52 hr duration. However, Shukla and Upadhyay (1989) noted that the essential oil of *Foeniculum volgare* and *Pimpenella anisum* exhibit insect repellent property against *T. castaneum* at 0.01 ml dose, which is much lesser than the result, mentioned here in

Cestrum species extract. Regarding antifeedant activity the results are quit promising as 5 ml dose caused complete inhibition in the feeding activity of *T. castaneum*. The results are similar as reported earlier by Jha et al., (1987) who noted response of *Adhatoda vasica* against *Sitophilus oryzae*. Similar observation have been made by Cunat et al., (1990) on the effect of some Mediterranean plants against *T. castaneum* and other insects. Dixit and Saxena et al (1992) on *Lantana camara* aginst *C. chinensis*. Further investigations are needed to find out the bioactive principal involved in *S. indicus* extract for repellent and antifeedant activity against *T. castaneum*.

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